

Functional Literacy Questionnaire (FLiQ)

Protocol of Administration and Scoring Procedure

The Functional Literacy Questionnaire (FLiQ) evaluates functional health literacy in 7th to 9th-grade adolescents (12+ years old). The FLiQ utilizes a food label that complies with the European Union Regulation; consequently, its administration is most suitable for the European context in terms of ecological validity.

The FLiQ is a self-administered questionnaire that can be applied in both online and paper-and-pen formats, provided that the layout remains consistent across both modalities, i.e., the information stimulus (food label) on the left and related items on the right (see the attached tool).

Applying the questionnaire implies sharing, with the research team (email: rfmartins@medicina.ulisboa.pt), the following information:

- Brief characterization of the sample where the FLiQ will be administered, namely sex (percentage of boys and girls) and age (mean/median, depending on what best suits the distribution of the dataset);
- Administration method (online or paper-and-pen);
- Sample size (after data collection);
- Internal consistency in the surveyed sample, using Kuder-Richardson Formula-20 (KR-20).

Here, we provide the questionnaire in Portuguese and English languages. However, it is important to note that the English version did not follow a back-translation process. Applying FLiQ in languages other than Portuguese implies the translation and cultural adaptation, following the World Health Organization guidelines: (1) forward translation (guided by detailed descriptions of the intent of each item); (2) expert panel meeting (for content validity appreciation); (3) backward translation; (4) pre-testing/cognitive interviewing; and (5) consensus on the final version.

The correction criteria for each FLiQ item are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Correction criteria for the Functional Literacy Questionnaire.

Item	Correct	Incorrect*
1	140 (only, kcal or similar)	-
2	2 (only, yogurts or portions) or 250 (only, g or ml)	½ yogurt or pack -
3	43 (only, g or similar)	-
4	7 or 8 (only or with %)	-
5	Almond	Because it can cause an allergic reaction Because the ingredients listed are the ones that you are allergic to Because it is bad for my health
6	To store between 0°C and 6°C	-
7	Wednesday	Up to two days
8	Salt or last line	-

*In addition to the options indicated, all “I don’t know” and missing answers should be considered incorrect.

The total score is derived by summing the correct answers (1 point for each) and ranges from 0 (no correct answers) to 8 (all correct answers). The total score is categorized into two health literacy levels: ‘limited’ (<5 points) and ‘adequate’ (≥5 points). Since the FLiQ aims to assess both numeracy and verbal comprehension skills, ‘adequate’ functional health literacy also implies responding correctly to at least two numeracy items (questions 1 to 4) and two verbal comprehension items (questions 5 to 8 of the FLiQ).

Lê este rótulo de uma embalagem de quatro iogurtes. Depois, responde às perguntas seguintes.

IOGURTE DE MORANGO E AMÊNDOA

INGREDIENTES: Leite pasteurizado, **leitelho**, morango e polme de morango 9%, **amêndoa** 1%, **fermentos lácteos**, concentrado de cenoura, sumo concentrado de limão, aromas, estabilizador (pectina) e conservante (sorbato de potássio). Origem: Portugal.

MODO DE CONSERVAÇÃO: Conservar entre 0°C e 6°C. Depois de aberto, manter no frio e consumir no prazo de 2 dias.

CONSUMIR ATÉ: Ver parte superior da embalagem.

DECLARAÇÃO NUTRICIONAL	POR 100g	POR PORÇÃO (125g)	% DOSE DE REFERÊNCIA* por porção	DOSE DIÁRIA DE REFERÊNCIA
ENERGIA	230 kJ 56 kcal	289 kJ 70 kcal	4 %	8400 kJ 2000 kcal
LÍPIDOS	1,5 g	1,9 g	3 %	70 g
DOS QUAIS SATURADOS	1,0 g	1,3 g	7 %	20 g
HIDRATOS DE CARBONO	5,7 g	7 g	3 %	260 g
DOS QUAIS AÇÚCARES	5,7 g	7 g	8 %	90 g
PROTEÍNAS	4,8 g	6 g	12 %	50 g
SAL	0,10 g	0,13 g	2 %	6 g

* Dose diária de referência para um adulto médio (8400 kJ / 2000 kcal)

Esta embalagem contém 4 porções, de 125g.

500g e
(4x125g)

1. Se comeres dois iogurtes, quantas calorias (kcal) vais consumir?

2. Se te disserem que só podes consumir 14 gramas de hidratos de carbono ao lanche, quantos iogurtes podes comer, assumindo que o lanche será composto apenas por iogurte?

3. Habitualmente consumes 50 gramas de açúcar por dia. Se deixares de comer uma porção deste iogurte, quantos gramas de açúcar passas a consumir por dia?

4. Para alguém que consuma 2000 calorias (kcal) por dia, que percentagem de calorias estará essa pessoa a consumir se comer duas porções deste iogurte?

5. Se tiveres alergia ao ovo, à amêndoa ou ao amendoim, por que é que não podes comer este iogurte?

6. O iogurte esteve no frigorífico a 8 graus nos últimos três dias. Por que razão não deves comer este iogurte?

7. Imagina que comeste metade de um iogurte na segunda-feira. Até que dia da semana poderias comer o resto do iogurte se o conservares no frigorífico?

8. Aconselharam-te a reduzir o consumo de sódio. Para o fazer, a que linha da declaração nutricional deves prestar atenção?

Read this label on a pack of four yogurts. Then, answer the following questions.

STRAWBERRY AND ALMOND YOGURT

INGREDIENTS: pasteurized milk, buttermilk, strawberry, and strawberry puree 9%, almond 1%, dairy ferments, carrot concentrate, concentrated lemon juice, flavorings, stabilizer (pectin) and preservative (potassium sorbate). Origin: Portugal.

STORAGE METHOD: Store between 0°C and 6°C. Once opened, keep in the cold and consume within 2 days.

CONSUME BY: See top of package.

NUTRITION FACTS	PER 100g	PER SERVING (125g)	% REFERENCE DOSE * per serving	REFERENCE DAILY DOSE
CALORIES	230 kJ 56 kcal	289 kJ 70 kcal	4 %	8400 kJ 2000 kcal
TOTAL FAT	1.5 g	1.9 g	3 %	70 g
SATURATED FAT	1.0 g	1.3 g	7 %	20 g
TOTAL CARBOHYDRATE	5.7 g	7 g	3 %	260 g
SUGARS	5.7 g	7 g	8 %	90 g
PROTEIN	4.8 g	6 g	12 %	50 g
SALT	0.10 g	0.13 g	2 %	6 g

* Daily reference dose for an average adult (8400 kJ / 2000 kcal).

This package contains 4 servings, weighing 125g.

500g e
(4x125g)

- If you eat two yogurts, how many calories (kcal) will you eat?

- If you are allowed to eat 14 grams of carbohydrates as a snack, how many yogurts will you eat, if the snack will only consist of yogurt?

- You usually eat 50 grams of sugar per day. If you stop eating one portion of this yogurt, how many grams of sugar would you consume each day?

- For someone who consumes 2000 calories (kcal) per day, what percentage of calories will that person be consuming if they eat two servings of this yogurt?

- Pretend that you are allergic to eggs, almonds, or peanuts. Why is it not safe to eat this yogurt?

- The yogurt was kept in the fridge at 8 degrees for the last three days. Why shouldn't you eat this yogurt?

- Imagine you ate half a yogurt on Monday. Until what day of the week could you eat the rest of the yogurt if you keep it in the fridge?

- You were advised to reduce sodium intake. To do this, which line of the nutritional declaration should you pay attention to?
